

Validation of the ‘Virtual Lysimeter’, a decision support system for soil grown greenhouse crops

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Abstract

Strict rules are in force for Dutch greenhouse horticulture to reduce water bound emissions. For soil-grown crops a ‘duty of care’ to tune fertigation to the crop demand is imposed. To enable growers to meet this requirement the ‘virtual lysimeter’ (VL) has been developed as DSS. It consists of a combination of an ET model and a soil model. By analogy to a physical lysimeter, the VL represents a specific soil-crop situation and the associated in- and outputs of water flows. The combination of ET model and soil model creates a powerful tool for growers that takes site-specific soil analysis and climate computer data and shows the grower a detailed water balance overview as well as a potential leaching for the next irrigation event. The VL presents three succinct graphics with the cumulative values of irrigation, ET, calculated leaching, and capillary flow; the course of the calculated moisture content in the individual three soil layers; and the instantaneous flows between layers. This gives the grower insight into his soil conditions and allows for tuned and optimized fertigation aiming at minimal leaching. Since water flows are the means of transport for nutrients and plant protection products (PPPs), this tool can be used to control emissions in a targeted way and reduce them to minimum proportions. This paper focuses on the validation of the VL in commercial greenhouses where physical lysimeters were installed. During an initial phase, the model was calibrated using physical lysimeters. In a second phase, the VL was validated for two years at two commercial greenhouses, with chrysanthemum and with fruit vegetables, using the measured leachates of the installed physical lysimeters.

Keywords: drainage, irrigation scheduling, leaching, lysimeter, soil model, water flow

INTRODUCTION

The quality of surface water in the Netherlands does not meet the chemical and ecological standards as indicated by the EU Water Framework Directive, as has been reported by Van Gaalen et al. (2016). Greenhouse horticulture in the Netherlands covers an area of nearly 10,000 ha (Raaphorst, 2017), located mainly in the western part of the country. The sector is characterized by high production rates and accordingly high inputs of nutrients as well as plant protection products (PPPs) in comparison with other agricultural sectors (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; Tiktak et al., 2019). These high inputs induce losses to ground and surface waters by leaching. Technical innovations and legislation, like the obligatory reuse of drainage for soilless culture systems, has led to a considerable reduction in the losses from greenhouses since 1994, but drainage water quality standards are still surpassed in many places (Van Gaalen et al., 2016). As a result, more strict rules have been implemented for Dutch greenhouse horticulture to reduce emissions of nutrients and PPPs from greenhouses. For soilless culture, it is mandatory to reuse all drainage water. This requirement cannot be imposed on soil-grown crops since drainage systems are not generally applicable, due to the big differences in hydrological situations between farms; moreover, these systems are inadequate to collect leachates completely (van der Salm et al., 2020). Furthermore, the potential risk of salinity due to the intrusion of brackish groundwater imply that there is no general basis to make reuse of drainage obligatory. Therefore, soil-grown crops have been given a specific regulation: a ‘duty of care’ to tune fertigation to the crop demand (Besluit

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Glastuinbouw, 2002). Although soilless culture is by far the main cropping system in Dutch greenhouse horticulture, a reasonable area is still used for soil-grown crops. The area as estimated from the Dutch agricultural area registrations is roughly 1200 ha, (10 -12% of the total greenhouse area) (Raaphorst, 2017). The main crops are cut-flowers, leafy-vegetables, and organically grown crops (Voogt, 2015).

An obvious solution for soil-grown crops would be a switch to soilless culture, however, this is for various technical and economic reasons not feasible (van der Salm et al., 2020). The most effective way to reduce leaching is to decrease the input of water and fertilizers although a certain amount of over-irrigation is the common irrigation strategy for soil grown crops to avoid salt accumulation. Voogt et al. (2000) demonstrated in several experiments with chrysanthemum in a Dutch commercial greenhouse that – provided the water quality meets strict standards – irrigation could be safely reduced to approach zero leaching. The approach of ‘tuning to crop demand’ as it is named, has been advocated by many stakeholders (water boards, local governments, grower organizations) as the most effective approach to minimize emissions. However, the water requirements of the crop and other important parameters such as soil moisture content and water retention capacity of the soil is unknown by growers, and they even are unaware of the leaching from their soil. Accordingly, the Dutch government, in cooperation with other stakeholders, launched a program focused on the development and implementation of tools to provide growers with insight in the demand of crops, the soil moisture conditions and the processes of leaching (Voogt et al., 2000). One such tool resulting from this program is the decision support system (DSS) ‘Virtual Lysimeter’ (VL) (Stoenner and Voogt, 2023). The VL focused on the irrigation only because control of the downward flow limits the outflow of both nutrients and PPPs. The connection was made with a previous project in which the concept of a physical lysimeter was applied as a tool to make leaching tangible (Voogt et al., 2015). For various technical reasons, this concept was not applicable in practice. However, insight gained by use of physical lysimeters into the hydrology of a soil profile proved to be a good starting point for growers and formed the basis for using a soil model as part of the DSS. The resulting model-based DSS was validated and fine-tuned over a two-year period using physical lysimeters installed at two commercial greenhouses, one with year-round crops of chrysanthemum (*Dendranthema × morifolium* Ramat.) and another with organically grown sweet pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Virtual Lysimeter

The Virtual Lysimeter (VL) DSS uses the approach of the crop-soil water balance. The core algorithms consist of a crop evapotranspiration model (ETM) and a soil-water balance model (SWM). The general approach of the VL is the mass balance of one virtual m² of a specific greenhouse area (irrigation valve group) to a soil depth of 90 cm, where the input is the irrigation (drip or sprinkler) (I_c), the output of the ETM is the crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) and the resulting surplus or deficit between I_c and ET_c (S_f) is applied into the soil, where it is becoming part of the water distribution and retention over three layers and eventually result in leachate or drainage (D_s). The VL uses climate computer data, parameter settings, and soil and crop data to simulate the flow of water into and out of the individual soil layers. Soil physical properties were analysed per layer. Soil parameters and greenhouse configuration parameters are entered per user. Solar radiation, greenhouse temperature, heating pipe temperature, screen positions and lighting (5 min data) are automatically uploaded per user. The ET_c is determined by the ETM according to the equations of de Graaf and van den Ende (1981), with modifications according to Voogt et al. (2000). Crop specific empirical factors (C_c) are derived from various experiments and are now available for 19 different crops (Voogt and Stoenner, 2023). The main driver for ET_c is the radiation sum (R), which is a combination of solar radiation, and supplemental lighting. Solar radiation from climate computer input values is proportionally reduced by i) a transmission factor, which is determined by specific values of the greenhouse cover, the sun-, energy- or black-out screens used, and ii) by the screen positions (open - closed), available from the climate computer.

Supplemental lighting is calculated based on the capacity installed and the time used. Each source of radiation is converted to $\text{J cm}^{-2} \text{ 5 min}^{-1}$ and added as a single radiation input into the VL. The influence of pipe heating on ETc is adjusted by the number of pipes and pipe diameter relative to the parameters in the equation in de Graaf and van den Ende (1981). Irrigation data are supplied by climate computers as L m^{-2} . The actual irrigation is buffered for the model for the input into the first soil layer according to a parameter 'max gift intensity' in L m^{-2} per 5 min to prevent an overly large pressure difference between L_1 and L_2 . For practical reasons, the SWM uses a simplified approach of the soil-water flow as more complex models like SWAP (Kroes et al., 2000) simulates vertical transport by Richard's equations including a range of lower boundary conditions like fluctuating groundwater levels in response to irrigation or rainfall, which would take far too much computation time for use in a practical web-based DSS. The soil in the SWM is broken into three layers, being 0-30, 30-60 and 30-90 cm (L_1 , L_2 , L_3 , respectively) and the vertical transport of water is simulated in unsaturated soils, determined by water pressure difference between layers described in Assinck and van der Salm (2011). It is designed to simulate flow and transport processes at field scale, during growing seasons and for longer term time series. The water flow between the subsequent layers is referred to as F_{L12} , F_{L23} , F_{L3d} for being the water flow from L_1 into L_2 , L_2 into L_3 and L_3 to drain, respectively. The pressure head and water retention characteristics of each layer are described by 'van Genuchten' equations (van Genuchten, 1980), including a lower boundary condition imposed by groundwater level. These equations are adapted to the specific soil and soil layers according to the method described by Wösten and Van Genuchten (1988) using the specific physical properties (soil texture and organic matter contents of the individual layers). From the equations, the soil moisture content of each layer θ_{L1} , θ_{L2} , and θ_{L3} is derived with the water content expressed in $\text{cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at the middle of L_1 , L_2 and L_3 , respectively. Initial values for each simulation are calculated for a balanced state, using an initial period with zero in- and output, and thereafter values result from F_{L12} , F_{L23} , and F_{L3d} as determined by climate computer inputs throughout the cropping cycle. The cumulative F_{L3d} being the eventual result of both downward and upward (capillary rise) fluxes over time are considered as the calculated drainage D_s .

Validation trials with physical lysimeter

Two commercial greenhouses, which have had a physical lysimeter installed for 6 years, were selected. These lysimeters, made from 8-mm polyester, were placed in a dug out of the same size (2.2 by 1.6 m and 0.9 m deep) on a representative location in the greenhouse and refilled – as much as possible – per layer with the same quantity of soil dug out of the original soil. The top of the lysimeter wall was reinforced with a rim of 2-mm stainless steel and was cleared regularly from the adjacent greenhouse soil to prevent capillary connection between in- and outside the lysimeter. The bottom of the lysimeter drained out into a pit with a pumping and measuring device. Drainage from the lysimeter (D_m) was measured daily. The lysimeters are described in detail in Voogt et al. (2015). Irrigation was provided by overhead sprinklers (chrysanthemum crop) or by drip irrigation combined with low hanging sprinklers (sweet pepper and tomato). The sprinklers and drip irrigation nozzles at the lysimeter were configured such that they would receive proportional amounts of water representative for the surface area, which was also calibrated before the start of the trials. The crops in the lysimeter were planted and treated equally to the crop in the greenhouse and crop management was performed according to the common standards for either chrysanthemum or organic sweet pepper and tomato. The growers scheduled the irrigation according to their own insights and experiences.

The first greenhouse, at Bleiswijk (DD 52.017089, 4.517972), had chrysanthemum year-round. The soil was a light clay-soil with a stable groundwater table at a 90 cm depth. Chrysanthemum crops were grown in sequence of approximately 65 days, where harvesting was usually followed by planting the same or the next day. During the evaluated period, 11 crops were monitored. The greenhouse was equipped with sun- and black-out screens and artificial lighting (SON-T, $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), which was used mainly during the period from September to March, both day and night (20 h) at the long-day phase of the crop and at

daylight period at the short-day phase (10.5 h) throughout each crop. Subsequently, the blackout screens were closed during the short-day dark period to allow max 10.5 h of daylight. Irrigation was applied by sprinklers with a capacity of 1.5 mm min⁻¹ and manually programmed. The typical schedule for chrysanthemum was applied and included: 3 mm right after planting, followed after 2-3 days by a peak irrigation (15-25 mm) meant to rewet the dried-out soil, followed by approximately six weeks of normal irrigation events (3-9 mm) with 2- to 5-day intervals, followed by a drying out period for the last 10 to 14 days before harvest. Irrigation intervals and quantities depended on the season and the actual climate conditions and irrigation was applied at night, in rounds of maximum 3 mm with 1- to 2-h intervals.

The second greenhouse was located at Velden (DD 51.419765, 6.197736), produced organic vegetables, and had a sandy soil with a ground water table varying between >2 m in summer and 1.5 m in winter. Sweet pepper was planted on January 10, 2021 and terminated on November 25, 2021, followed by tomato, which started with prolonged propagation in the greenhouse on January 6, 2022, planting in the soil on February 15, and terminated on November 15, 2022. The greenhouse was equipped with a standard pipe heating system and a sun-energy screen. Irrigation was applied by one dripper, with a capacity of 1.5 L h⁻¹ plant⁻¹, and in addition by low hanging sprinkler irrigation at 10 cm above the ground with one nozzle with a capacity of 1 mm min⁻¹. Drip irrigation was used during the first two months and sprinkler irrigation thereafter. Irrigation was scheduled depending on the plant size and radiation sum, with pulses for the drip irrigation events of maximum 5 min. (0.3 mm) and for sprinkler irrigation events of 3 to 10 min (5-15 mm) at 2- to 5-day intervals and applied in rounds of maximum 5 mm with 1- to 2-h intervals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the validation study for 11 individual chrysanthemum crops showed that for some crops the total simulated and measured drainage (D_s and D_m) for the full cropping period was quite similar, but in other cases the difference between the two was considerable (Table 1). However, over time D_s and D_m followed the same pattern, as can be seen clearly in the example presented of one year with five consecutive chrysanthemum crops, from November 12, 2020 to October 28, 2021 (Figure 1). Clearly visible is the seasonal effect on the development of ET_c and I_c . All five crops showed a significant S_f ($I_c - ET_c$). The results of D_s and D_m are quite well matched in three of the five crops and clearly all follow the same pattern. This is also the case for the full cropping season of sweet pepper, but with the following tomato crop, the difference between D_s and D_m was significantly larger (Figure 2), while S_f was much smaller for both organic vegetable crops compared to chrysanthemum. There appeared to be a good relationship between D_s and D_m when drainage is averaged over a weekly period, though comparison on a daily basis results in quite large spreading (Figure 3). There are clear reasons for D_s and D_m to be different. Firstly, the specific irrigation schedule for chrysanthemum includes a peak irrigation event (15-25 mm) for rewetting the dried-out soil, followed by normal irrigation events of (3-9 mm) at 2- to 5-day intervals (season dependent), and the 10- to 14-day period before harvest without irrigation. The simplified SWM does not consider physical changes of the soil (swelling, shrinking) affected by the alternating dry and wet periods, such as macropore formation, which may create bypass flow for irrigation water and cause greater flow rates than simulated. Secondly, the model also does not consider the interception of overhead sprinkler irrigation by the crop canopy, which does not enter the soil surface, especially not for short irrigation events. For the final water balance of the crop, this will hardly play a role, since the water intercepted by the foliage reduces ET_c to the same extent; however, in the SWM it will directly affect the simulated waterflows. There may also be errors in the measured drainage. Due to technical limitations, the measurement is only at a fixed time daily. It may therefore be that a specific D_m flux is not measured until almost 24 h later than the model calculated $F_{L,3d}$. In addition, the macropores mentioned above can also be disruptive, when part of the irrigation is measured more quickly in the lysimeter than is reflected in the calculation.

Table 1. The total sum of irrigation, evapotranspiration (ET), simulated drainage (D_s) and measured drainage (D_m) all in mm and the % of D_m explained by D_s of 11 successive chrysanthemum crops.

Specifications	Crop number										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Start date	13-11	28-01	08-04	23-06	03-09	11-11	26-01	05-04	15-06	25-08	04-11
End date	25-01	06-04	18-06	25-08	11-11	25-01	04-04	14-06	22-08	03-11	17-01
Irrigation	180	152	316	322	185	139	197	287	304	240	154
ET	115	168	268	278	163	116	168	201	257	184	89
Drain simulated	62	17	22	42	34	27	40	75	68	65	54
Drain measured	62	26	42	36	44	29	65	58	78	66	42
Ds:Dm (%)	101	64	51	118	75	92	62	131	86	97	128

Figure 1. Course of the cumulative values of irrigation (I_c), evapotranspiration (ET_c), simulated drainage (D_s), and measured drainage (D_m) of five consecutive chrysanthemum crops from early November 2020 to the end of October 2021 (crop 6-10 from Table 1).

Figure 2. Course of the cumulative values of irrigation (I_c), evapotranspiration (ET_c), simulated drainage (D_s), and measured drainage (D_m) of a sweet pepper (January 2021-November 2021) and tomato crop (February 2022-November 2022).

Figure 3. Scatterplots of the simulated drainage (D_s) from the virtual lysimeter compared to the measured drainage (D_m) by the lysimeter of the daily sum (left graph) or weekly sum (right graph) for 11 chrysanthemum crops.

Another complication is that the lysimeter was disconnected from the groundwater and saturated zone due to the sealed bottom. Capillary rise could therefore not occur which resulted in drying out of the lysimeter during periods with a negative water flow, and in subsequent periods with positive flow, drainage would be postponed in relation to that simulated. Such a pattern can be seen clearly in the results of the tomato crop (Figure 2). In the first three months S_f is negative, after this point S_f is continuously positive, with an eventual difference of about 40 mm more I_c than ET_c . This results in a positive D_s , shortly from the moment the cumulative $I_c > ET_c$, while the D_m increases more than a month later and lags behind D_s . In addition, it should be noted that the tomato crop starts in the first four weeks in pots on plates, isolated from the soil (prolonged propagation period), and is only connected to the soil when planted during week 5; the VL has no mechanism to simulate this behaviour.

Figure 4. Course of the cumulative irrigation, ET_c , D_s , (top), the simulated dynamics of the water flows into the three soil layers F_{12} to F_{23} , F_{3D} together with the actual irrigation events (middle) and the simulated soil moisture contents θ_{L1} , θ_{L2} , θ_{L3} during chrysanthemum crop 10 (bottom).

The output of the model provides clear insight into the water balance of a crop, both for any stage during a cropping cycle period (Figure 4) as well as for the dynamic progression during the growing period (Figures 1 and 2). In particular, the cumulative display of both I_c , ET_c and D_s from the start of a crop makes a water deficit or surplus clearly visible. For many growers, knowledge of soil moisture conditions is restricted to the upper layer of the topsoil. What is happening in the deeper soil layers below remains out of sight and if leaching is occurring it is not at all visible. The VL has the potential to generate much more insight into the dynamics of the moisture in the soil. In addition, displaying the dynamics of the moisture content in the three soil layers and the waterfluxes over the three soil layers will greatly increase the understanding and awareness of potential leaching (Figure 4). The example given shows how irrigation rounds increase θ_{L1} immediately, followed by a delayed increase in F_{12} and θ_{L2} , and a successively longer delay before F_{23} increases θ_{L3} and F_{3d} finally shows leaching from the soil. θ_{L3} hardly changes, which is obvious for being constantly high in water content due to close proximity to groundwater (90 cm for chrysanthemum). By keeping track of the course of the calculated soil moisture contents, a grower will have a clear insight whether his soil is drying out or becoming more saturated.

CONCLUSIONS

Generally speaking, growers of soil-bound greenhouse crops are unaware of the water balance of their crop and soil and more specifically the water flows and losses by leaching. Within this context, innovative technologies could be considered as useful tools to support the daily management of irrigation strategies with the general goal to optimize the application of water. The main aim of the VL is to give the user insight into the dynamic water balance in the soil and the water management of their crop with an eye towards that balance. The VL supports growers on the right timing and amount of irrigation. By monitoring the progress of the various parameters over time, they can also adjust the irrigation strategy based on earlier irrigation decisions. The graphical output of the data are ideally suited for this purpose. The VL model was able to produce fairly reliable simulations of water leached out from the soil. For more than half of the individual chrysanthemum crops and for the pepper crop, the deviation from the measured leaching was limited. For the crops where the deviation was greater, such as the tomato crop and part of the chrysanthemum crops, a technical explanation can also be given. In view of the overall purpose of the VL, it can be concluded that the VL can be considered a viable DSS for irrigation planning in soil-grown greenhouse. It should be mentioned though that the reliability of VL is strongly affected by the quality and accuracy of the selected data and parameters and will improve greatly if its implementation is accompanied by site-specific calibration of the irrigation flow meters and the measured radiation at plant canopy level (the effective greenhouse transmissivity). Finally, end-users must be trained to interpret the results and respond to the signals given by the DSS.

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